

STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTIONS OF EMISSIONS REPORTING IN THE FINNISH LOGISTICS SECTOR

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1. INTRODUCTION

Achieving the targeted reductions in greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) requires the implementation of a broad range of measures both within the European Union (EU) and at the global level. The EU aims to reduce net GHG emissions, compared to those in 1990, by at least 55% by 2030 and by 90% by 2040. With these milestones, the EU aims to attain climate neutrality by 2050 (European Commission, 2025a). Finland has committed to reduce GHG emissions from the transport sector by 50% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, with the objective of achieving zero emissions by 2045 at the latest (Jääskeläinen, 2021). Further, emissions reduction targets related to freight transport require that companies are first able to quantify both their direct (Scopes 1 & 2) and indirect supply chain emissions (Scope 3) (World Resources Institute, 2011) and are willing to implement different measures to develop more environmentally sustainable logistics. Improved logistics data-sharing practices and comparable emissions data are crucial enablers that support policy-driven emission mitigation targets (Stenzel & Waichman, 2023).

Emissions calculation and reporting can be used to monitor development and correctly address target measures. As the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) already obliges larger companies to perform sustainability reporting in the EU, emissions reporting in the logistics sector has become a rather topical issue (European Commission, 2025b). In addition, the requirement of broader systemic change has been noted (WEF, 2021) which calls for action by numerous different stakeholders, collaboration with competitors (Karam et al., 2021), and acknowledging the role of buying power (Kim et al., 2014) from clients of freight transport companies that share coherent long-term sustainability targets. Wieland and Creutzig (2025) highlight the urgent need to enhance knowledge sharing and collaborative efforts among buyers and their suppliers. In similar vein, Stenzel and Waichman (2023) emphasise that efficient data sharing is essential for calculating and reducing Scope 3 emissions, which are the indirect emissions produced by a company's complex and multilayered supplier networks.

In extant literature in the field, the role of emission data and environmental reporting has been identified as an important enabler of reducing emissions in logistics (McKinnon, 2021). It is also recognised that companies are increasingly prioritising environmental considerations, including the assessment and calculation of carbon emissions, in logistics operations (e.g. Bauer et al., 2024). Previous studies have also discussed the benefits and targets of emission data usage (Doda et al., 2016; Dragomir, 2012; du Plessis et al., 2022). Moreover, it is acknowledged that companies face various challenges related to emission calculations and the utilisation of emission data (Kallionpää et al., 2024; Pfoser, 2022; Shaw et al., 2021). The perspectives of logistics service providers' (LSPs) and shippers' have been taken into account both in combination and individually in green logistics studies (e.g. Huge-Brodin et al., 2020), but not particularly focusing on emissions reporting and involving the multistakeholder perspective. There is also a real-life gap related to the transparency of emissions data, which also reveals that more research is needed to enable the development of emission calculation and reporting. This study aims to fill these gaps. In addition, futures research methods have not been widely used when studying green logistics. There is substantial potential of utilising futures thinking and various futures research methods such as scenarios and Delphi method when considering long-term (10+ years) issues related to green logistics and, in this case, in developing logistics emissions reporting from the multistakeholder perspective. In this study, the Futures Triangle method by which the three competing forces – the pull of the future, the push of the present, and the weight of past – can be addressed simultaneously (Inayatullah, 2023) is applied as a novel approach in this field.

The aim of this study is to present stakeholders' perceptions of the current state and future prospects of the development of emissions reporting in the logistics sector, with a specific focus on Finland. The study adopts a holistic approach, which aims to broadly explore stakeholders in the Finnish logistics sector. Thus, this study examines the readiness of heterogeneous companies, the challenges associated with emissions reporting, and the utilisation of emissions data as well as future prospects in this regard. Moreover, this study focuses on identifying the main elements related to the long-term change required to the rather siloed current practises of implementing high-quality emissions data procedures as well as highlighting the importance of emissions data transparency from a broader systemic perspective. In line with previous studies (e.g. Rebs et al., 2017; Siems et al., 2022), this study explores the development of emissions reporting from a multistakeholder perspective, which includes traditional stakeholders such as LSPs and shippers, as well as contribution from non-traditional stakeholders (regulatory and governance bodies, information and communication technology (ICT) service providers, consultants, and research institutes).

This research seeks answers to the following research questions (RQ):

- RQ1: What is the current state and future prospects of the emissions calculation and reporting in the logistics sector in Finland?
- RQ2: How can the Futures Triangle method be utilised to structure the complex topic of emissions reporting and improve the understanding of coherent long-term trajectories towards achieving mutual emission goals in logistics sector?

The remainder of this paper is structured in the following manner. After this introductory section, Section 2 presents the literature review. Section 3 outlines the methods, and Section 4 presents the results. Section 5 details the discussion and concluding remarks.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Logistics is an essential aspect of companies' business and operations, and logistics operations have substantial environmental impacts. Due to ambitious emission reduction targets as well as stakeholders' growing interest in sustainability, decarbonising logistics has become increasingly important, thereby prompting companies to adopt sustainable strategies and implement green actions (Hettler & Graf-Vlachy, 2024; McKinnon, 2021). Achieving emission targets requires various green actions. Logistics emissions monitoring and reporting are natural starting points for reducing emissions in the logistics sector (McKinnon, 2021). Indeed, interest in carbon emission calculation and emissions data has gradually increased among companies (Bauer et al., 2024). Digital tools enable better collection and analysis of accurate emissions data throughout the supply chain, thereby facilitating more precise emissions monitoring and environmental reporting (Lähde et al., 2020).

LSPs are central to supply chain operations, and their sustainable development is crucial for achieving overall sustainability (Laari et al., 2018). LSPs are willing to adopt green practices, but implementation is strongly dependent on financial support from logistics customers (Prataviera et al., 2024). Moreover, many LSPs appear to emphasise regular emissions reporting, but they are still in the early stages of overall sustainable development in their operations (Wehner et al., 2021). The level of sustainability and emissions reporting practices also varies considerably among both LSPs and shippers (Ellram et al., 2022; Lambrechts et al., 2019). For example, certain shippers do not report their emissions to third parties at all (Ellram et al., 2022). With regard to emissions data, there is substantial potential to gain value. Emissions data and environmental reporting can be used to monitor the actual development of GHG emissions and the green actions needed to reduce emissions in logistics (Doda et al., 2016). Accurate emissions reporting is also essential for setting targets to achieve emission reductions (Rietbergen et al., 2015). Emissions data can be used to estimate overall carbon emissions, report emissions to stakeholders, and predict the amount of carbon emissions in a customer's shipment (du Plessis et al., 2022). Environmental reporting can also be valuable for a company's communications and marketing (Doda et al., 2016; Dragomir, 2012). In addition, Dobers et al. (2019) state that shippers' tendering processes may prefer LSPs that provide actual emissions data.

Extant literature in the field identifies several factors that affect green actions and carbon emissions reporting. Customer and other stakeholder demands and interest in sustainability have been identified as important drivers of emissions reporting (Hettler & Graf-Valchy, 2024; Lambrechts et al., 2019; Prataviera et al., 2024). Based on the stakeholder theory, stakeholder support and acceptance are prerequisites for the continued existence of a company (Lambrechts et al., 2019). The involvement of various stakeholders is understood to influence the adoption of green logistics practices (GLPs) (Huge-Brodin et al., 2020). Customers and suppliers are vital, but the relevance of final consumers and competitors is increasing in parallel with awareness of environmental sustainability (Prataviera et al., 2024).

Marketing, investor pressures, and corporate governance are also drivers of emissions reporting (Hettler & Graf-Valchy, 2024). The government and related authorities play key roles in this regard as well (Kallionpää et al., 2024). Regulatory pressure and

guidelines are among the strongest factors that influence companies to engage in carbon emission reporting (Tang & Demeritt, 2018). The lack of measurements standards and regulations negatively affect companies' willingness to adopt GLPs (Prataviere et al., 2024). Jazairy and von Haartman (2020) highlight that stricter regulations would motivate shippers to have higher green practice demands on LSPs. Further, sustainability-oriented organisational culture and long-term managerial commitment are recognised as important enablers of green development and environmental responsiveness (Jazairy & von Haartman, 2020; Pham et al., 2024). According to Dobers et al. (2019), the major barriers to transport emission calculations include challenges in data collection and exchange, the availability of default data, methodological issues, motivational barriers, information asymmetry, and implementation costs. Previous studies have identified a lack of long-term strategic planning (Bosman et al., 2018) and insufficient goal-oriented trajectories towards a low-carbon future (Pyykkö et al., 2021) among logistics sector stakeholders, thus contributing to inertia and resistance to change. With regard to emissions reporting, Kallionpää et al. (2024) found the following challenges to be the most significant: comparability of data, lack of resources, lack of know-how and experience, lack of political guidance, disregarding the importance of emissions reporting data, and different development phases of emissions reporting in heterogenous companies.

3. METHODS

This paper is based on qualitative research methods. Qualitative research is useful for exploring the quality and meanings of phenomena (Islam & Aldaihani, 2022; Lim, 2023), and the participatory approach advocates actively involving the research participants in the research process (Armanto et al., 2022). Workshops are used to facilitate group processes to deal with actual challenges that concern groups (Vidal, 2006). In addition to conducting a literature review, a face-to-face stakeholder workshop was organised as a participatory research method in Finland in January 2025. The workshop was a follow-up to the workshop organised in Autumn 2023, which examined challenges and solutions towards ideal emissions reporting (Kallionpää et al., 2024). It was noted that more research is needed in this context, and this study responds to that need with a new approach. In the literature review, the focus was on understanding the perspectives regarding and the development of emissions calculation and reporting in the logistics sector. The aim of the workshop was to discuss and reflect with heterogenous logistics stakeholders regarding the development of logistics emissions calculation and reporting among companies. The approach in the workshop was futures-oriented and the Futures Triangle method was applied. As Futures Triangle has a logical, suitable, and simple visual presentation and can bring out tensions as well as interactions among different actors, it was considered the most suited to serve the needs of the workshop.

The participants of the workshop were selected through careful mapping and purposeful sampling (Saunders et al., 2019) in accordance with the holistic approach of the study to broadly cover the logistics sector. The heterogenous participants of the workshop were representatives from different logistics stakeholders: trade and industrial companies (four representatives), LSPs (eight representatives), authorities (five representatives), associations (three representatives), consultants (four representatives), and other professionals (e.g. researchers—six representatives) in the field of logistics. Trade and industrial companies (shippers) represent the most

significant industries in Finland. One of the shippers was from the trade sector, one from the steel industry, one from the forest industry and one from the food industry. The logistics and transport companies represented were medium-sized and large companies that provide different transport and logistics services (e.g. road haulage, freight forwarding, and contract logistics). The views of heterogeneous participants were collected to provide a holistic overview of the logistics sector in Finland. The participating companies also run international logistics operations; thus, the results of the workshop can be generalised beyond Finland. During the workshop, the 30 participants and 4 facilitators were divided into 4 small groups. Groups were formed so that different stakeholders were represented in each group. Each of the four groups had their own facilitator.

In the workshop, the Futures Triangle method was employed to address the current state of development as well as future development of logistics emissions calculation and reporting and the barriers and challenges related to the utilisation of emissions data (Figure 2). The Futures Triangle is an analytical framework which helps to establish the big picture and rich view of changes and recognise the desired futures and barriers to change. In the workshop in 1997 from which the method originates the aim was to link the emerging vision of the future with trends and the ground reality (Inayatullah, 2023), which was also the idea in our workshop related emissions calculation and reporting.

Inayatullah (2023) defines the Futures Triangle as a simple method that is used to map three competing factors: the pull of the future (the vision), the push of the present (current trends), and the weight of past (the forces that hamper change and are tied to the current state as well as the obstacles and barriers to achieving different futures). According to the method, brainstorming on these three dimensions is used to encourage a discussion regarding possible futures produced by the interaction of the above-mentioned three factors (Fergnani, 2020), where the future appears as a contested space among these three (Inayatullah, 2003). Alternative names may be used for the angles of the triangle—for example, the push of the present can be referred to as the enabler and the weight of past as the barrier of change for those who are business-oriented (Inayatullah, 2023). It has been generally argued (IRENA, 2024) that the freight transport sector is a hard-to-abate sector in terms of decarbonisation, with a long-term historical dependence on fossil-fuel usage. Thus, this paper notes the importance of comprehending and involving the weight of the past that reflects the barriers and challenges to building a more holistic understanding of how decarbonisation measures can be implemented.

Further, as a mapping technique, the Futures Triangle can be used to obtain insight into the system as it is, based on the current image of the future. The method can be used to develop strategy, for policymaking, and as a stand-alone futures method or in conjunction with other methods, such as emerging issues analysis or scenarios. (Inayatullah, 2023) For example, Fergnani (2020) introduced Futures Triangle 2.0, which integrates the original method with scenario planning by visually representing scenarios against the three dimensions of the Triangle. Once the future is mapped using the Futures Triangle, the participants or researchers can develop strategies to clarify the vision or navigate the waves of change. Moreover, the method can be utilised to map, for example, the preferred or plausible future. Unlike what is presented

in most figures, the Futures Triangle does not have to be equilateral (Inayatullah, 2023).

During the workshop, the three dimensions of the Futures Triangle were discussed. We began discussions in each of the four groups with the dimension of the push of the present, considering the current state of emissions reporting and the utilisation of emissions data in the logistics sector. After that the weight of the past was discussed. The participants were specifically asked to consider what kind of challenges and barriers are currently associated with emissions reporting. Finally, the participants discussed their views on the future of emissions calculations and reporting as well as the use of emissions data. During the discussions, it was possible to return to different dimensions and discuss them simultaneously to enable open and fruitful discussions. We had reserved one hour for these discussions. At the beginning of the discussions, the participants spent approximately five minutes for quiet independent work to write down their own thoughts on Post-it® notes. Thereafter, things were discussed with the entire group, and the facilitators took notes. The Futures Triangle framework used in the workshop was printed on paper on the tables (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Futures Triangle framework contextualised for the workshop.

After the workshop, the notes from the four discussion workshop groups were combined, and the results of the workshop were analysed using qualitative content analysis. The identified elements in each Futures Triangle dimension were further divided into groups according to the socio-technical hexagon framework (Davis et al., 2014) to provide a more descriptive structure. The framework comprises six interrelated dimensions that facilitate the analysis of socio-technical systems: *Goals*, describing the aims and vision of a desirable future; *People*, referring to individuals and groups, including their skills and interactions; *Culture*, representing shared values and dominant norms; *Processes*, involving routines and operational procedures; *Technology*, including technological components; and *Infrastructure*, encompassing physical structures—though this dimension falls outside the scope of this study.

4. RESULTS

In the following subsections, the results of the workshop are presented in accordance with the three forces of the Futures Triangle.

4.1 The push of the present

The question ‘*What is the current state of the development of emissions reporting and the utilisation of emission data in logistics sector?*’ sparked a lengthy discussion. First, it was noted that interest in and awareness of emission issues have increased and there is clear progress and a change process oriented towards the normalisation of emissions reporting in logistics. It was evident that over time, emissions reporting will become part of normal operations. However, participants raised several concerns related to the development of emissions reporting. One of the concerns is that there remains substantial variation in the implementation of reporting. Another concern highlighted is that there are differences in the capabilities of reporting in this context. These capabilities are related to expertise, resources, and equipment, and can vary substantially depending on the company. In general, there are many different operators and different types of transport services in the logistics sector. This complexity of the field and nature of logistics networks affects the level of emissions reporting.

During discussions regarding the variety of companies, it was noted that there are three kinds of companies. Certain companies are pioneers and aim to be development-oriented while others resist change. The remaining companies are somewhere in the middle, attempting to follow the leaders but may not have the capabilities to do that yet. The size of the company has also an effect on this—larger companies usually have better chances, for example, to allocate resources and invest compared to smaller companies. The participants also highlighted that the availability of data varies significantly. The lack of comparability and transparency is currently a significant challenge. The big concern is related to the fact that different countries use different emission factors and, therefore, the data is not commensurate. Moreover, it was also mentioned that processing and managing the data was challenging, as there is large amount of data that needs to be transferred among several different software. The discussions also brought up the need for cooperation among different stakeholders in the logistics sector, and the exchange of information on best practices are essential for the development of emissions reporting. Another important element identified by participants was the openness of data sharing to enhance transparency. The results of the discussion on the current state are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The results of the discussion on the current state.

Push of the present: Current state	
<p><i>Social</i></p> <p>People</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increasing interest in emission issues - need for cooperation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o exchange of best practices o openness with data sharing <p>Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - change process towards normalisation of emissions reporting - complexity of the logistics field 	<p><i>Technical</i></p> <p>Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - different capabilities - companies' varied development levels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o implementation of reporting - lack of comparability and transparency - data is not commensurate <p>Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - big amounts of data to be transferred

- numerous companies and different transport needs	
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4.2 The weight of the past

In next phase, the participants were asked to consider the weight of the past that influenced the development of logistics emissions reporting with the help of the following question: *‘What kind of challenges do you currently recognise related to emissions calculation and reporting in logistics sector?’* Several issues were discussed and identified. One such issue was the effect of unfamiliarity. Monitoring and reporting emissions is quite a new aspect for several actors in the logistics field, which implies that there are no established practices yet; this leads to the challenge of varying reporting practices. Typically, the reporting style varies according to the customer. Existing habitual practices are the weight of the past. The lack of knowledge, resources, and motivation in many companies was highlighted as a challenge. The weight of the pursuit of perfection was also recognised. It was suggested that instead of reaching for perfection with calculation and reporting, the actors could begin with small steps and actions. There is no need to master everything right away.

Further, the general uncertainty related to the development of the reporting and green actions was also recognised among stakeholders. This uncertainty arises from the political and other emergence issues of the world, thereby making logistics actors slightly doubtful regarding the role of the development of sustainability issues, among others. As a positive signal, the participants mentioned that the development of digitalisation has somewhat reduced the weight of the past related to data handling, analyses, and sharing. However, emissions data is still not easily available, if available at all. One of the calculation challenges relates to the variation of initial data and emission factors, which are fundamental issues for reporting. Allocation in calculations, ambiguity of the standard, and reviewing the figures were also considered challenging. The identified challenges are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Identified challenges of logistics emissions calculation and reporting.

Weight of the past: Challenges	
<p><i>Social</i></p> <p>People</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of resources, know-how, and motivation <p>Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - novelty of the matter - existing practices and habits - striving for perfection - poor availability of emissions data <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - uncertainty of driving trends and policies 	<p><i>Technical</i></p> <p>Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - variety of practices - calculation challenges (etc. allocation, ambiguity of the standard, viewing figures) - lack of comparability and reliability of the data <p>Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of digital tools—development of digitalisation has reduced the weight of the past

4.3 The pull of the future

Finally, the participants were asked to consider the plans, dreams, and hopes for the future related to emission calculation and use of emission data. The question *‘What are your views on the future of emission calculation and the use of emission data?’* raised many thoughts and led to a fruitful discussion. Environmental requirements were envisioned to grow in the future in the logistics sector; therefore, it was also evident that the importance of sustainability reporting will likely grow. The participants highlighted that emission data will be the currency of the future and a key aspect of

business management and development. Furthermore, emissions data will likely be an important selection criterion for companies apart from costs. The calculation and use of emission data can also function as a competitive advantage as well as a vital means to reduce emissions in the logistics sector. Based on these discussions, it is evident that emissions monitoring and reporting will be one of the normal daily and strategic operations in companies in the logistics sector in the desired future. Moreover, advances in technology and digitalisation will enable this development. In the desired future, reporting will be automated and integrated into existing developed systems. In addition, related to common calculation methods, it was considered important that fill rates and empty runs are considered in future calculations.

However, the attainment of the desired future requires the fulfilment of certain vital boundary conditions. The participants emphasized that comprehensive standard-based verification as well as common rules and methods for calculation and reporting are needed. Coherent data sources are also vital. For example, the initial data for the calculation and reporting of emission factors should be common, but also country-specific, considering possible country-specific characteristics of logistics such as 76 tonnes articulated trucks allowed in Finland. However, such development needs the proactivity of actors and stakeholders. Further, cooperation, exchange of good practices, and transparency of data are essential. Overall, based on the discussions, there appears to be faith and confidence in sustainable development in the future in the logistics sector. Table 3 presents the discussed views and desired future of emissions reporting.

Table 3. Views and desired future of emissions reporting.

Pull of the future: Views and desired future	
<p><i>Social</i></p> <p>People</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strong cooperation - sharing good practices - proactive actors <p>Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increasing environmental demands - normalisation of emissions reporting - common rules <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - emission data as a future currency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o key aspect of management o selection criterion o competitive advantage 	<p><i>Technical</i></p> <p>Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - comprehensive verification - common emission factors - transparency - fill rates and empty runs in calculations - reliable data sources—national characteristics <p>Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - digitalisation - automatised reporting and use of data - emission data integrated into existing systems

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study investigated the role of improved and more transparent logistics emissions data from different stakeholder perspectives and the future potential to support broader decarbonisation efforts in this sector. This study provides novel answers to two research questions (RQ1 and RQ2) and further generates theoretical and managerial contributions as well as policy implications.

The findings related to RQ1 highlight the growing awareness and willingness among logistics sector actors to utilise emissions data and develop emissions reporting. However, various social and technology-related challenges were identified (see

Tables 1 and 2). The workshop results indicate that many of the stakeholders participating in our study adopt and focus on a future-oriented development approach to emissions data sharing and the utilisation of this data for further decision-making processes. Stakeholders also considered emissions data as a future asset (see Table 3), thereby implying that emissions data will be a critical element of business—providing competitive advantage and becoming a key selection decision criterion alongside costs. Such views indicate that the current state is still rather vague in this respect and the trajectory towards emission-transparent supply chains are still in the very early stages. We noted that each organisation (representatives who participated in the workshop) also has their individual sustainability strategies in terms of emissions data, which makes the status quo situation too fragmented to be explored more holistically. The available resources and company size appeared to influence how far the individual organisations are in the emissions data-sharing processes. While the regulation, recently implemented emissions calculation standards, and increasing overall awareness of climate change evidently support the implementation of coherent emissions data sharing, the workshop results revealed the existence of many persistent obstacles. The workshop results highlight various interdependencies among practices, processes, sustainability goals related to organisational cultures, and requirement for fit-for-purpose technological innovations for efficient emissions data-sharing in complex freight transport networks. These findings of multilayered challenges for change are similar to those noted in earlier reports (e.g. IRENA, 2024) that led to resistance towards the decarbonisation of the logistics sector.

Further, in our study, we identified four main challenges which need to be overcome for prior emissions data and reporting practices to be implemented at a sufficient level: (1) *Data availability and consistency*: The availability of emissions and input data remains highly variable. Moreover, emissions data are not standardised, which complicates comparability and integration across systems. (2) *Variability in reporting practices*: Emissions reporting practices and their implementation continue to vary significantly across organisations, thus indicating a lack of harmonised procedures. (3) *Gaps caused by different capabilities and data-sharing willingness of heterogeneous stakeholders within complex multinational supply chains*: Actors that are part of the transport chain exhibit differences in capabilities, including expertise and resource availability, which affect their ability to effectively engage with emissions reporting. (4) *Modest push for change caused by external drivers*: Increasing customer demands and the influence of competitive tendering processes are emerging as key drivers for the advancement of emissions reporting practices. Based on the workshop, the vision for the future is that emissions monitoring and reporting will become routine and standardised, supported by automation, digital integration, improved calculation methods, as well as comprehensive standard-based verification (see Table 3). Achieving this desired future will require particularly standardised methods, reliable and context-sensitive data, proactive stakeholder involvement, sharing good practices, transparency of data, and collaboration across the sector.

Regarding RQ2, the Futures Triangle method proved to be well-suited for the study, being a good method to structure issues and improve understanding regarding the development of emissions reporting in logistics. Workshop participants provided positive feedback regarding the method. Moreover, since there are numerous stakeholders in the logistics field, it is vital to take into account different perspectives of development, not merely a siloed view of a single actor. Thus, collaborative effort is

important, and the Futures Triangle method can be utilised to encourage open discussions among different stakeholders and, thus, create a synthesis of the ideas of different stakeholders and common visions and goals for the logistics sector. To develop emissions reporting, an understanding of the current state and challenges that need to be overcome need to be known. This knowledge is also the basis for creating future visions and vital long-term planning to achieve common targets. The Futures Triangle functions as a tool for these considerations; in this study, it enabled us to examine the research topic from different perspectives, thus bringing forth as many views as possible. During these discussions, we noticed that a few challenges related to logistics emissions calculation and reporting were already raised by participants while discussing the push of the present dimension, which is natural, and more challenges and barriers were highlighted while discussing the weight of the past dimension. This implies that the process of the method made it possible to structure the ideas and provided space for them to be expressed during the workshop. Moreover, this provided a good basis for further discussion on the plans, hopes, and views for the future.

For the research community, this study deepens the understanding regarding the development of logistics emissions reporting and provides a novel approach to view and understand holistic long-term trajectories towards a common desired future. The Futures Triangle method was utilised to view the complex research object from the perspective of long-term change. Based on the findings, this study emphasises that increased emission data transparency requires research on the interplay of both social and technical elements. Furthermore, the change involving emissions data as a new key performance indicator requires collaborative efforts among LSPs and a push from their industrial customers. This study also noted that stakeholders in the non-traditional logistics sector (e.g. authorities, research institutes, and consultants) play a crucial role in enabling sufficient emissions data-sharing practices. This study concludes that the research methods utilised in similar studies need to involve long-term change perspectives, holistic multistakeholder views, as well as both social and technical factors to be able to generate rigorous research results on such complex topics.

As a managerial contribution, the presented Futures Triangle method is also suitable for managers to support their decision-making and discuss futures-related issues. Furthermore, this study illustrates the current status and views on logistics emissions reporting and provides information to further develop this reporting. *For policymakers and authorities*, this study provides information on where progress has been made and what still needs to be done to support the development of emissions reporting. Moreover, the study provides information on the challenges in the field as well as the needs and wishes of companies related to the development of emissions reporting in the future. *For future research*, this study could be extended by creating and examining scenarios for future emissions reporting. Moreover, organising international workshops on the subject would deepen the understanding of perspectives and development in Europe and beyond and enable comparison among different countries.

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